

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

**St. Clements University Clinical Psychology PHD
Oya Kilic (ORCID-0000-0003-4714-9921)**

To cite this article: Oya Kılıç, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 3-5, 2023, p. 59 – 87. - 0099-0001-2303-0203.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

Post-traumatic stress disorder is a debilitating psychological condition that can develop in some individuals following trauma. Examples of trauma include serious accidents, natural or man-made disasters, life-threatening illnesses, or physical or sexual assault. To be diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder, an individual must show signs of aggression, avoidance, negative changes in cognitions and mood, and changes in arousal and reactivity in response to a traumatic experience. Studies have shown that individuals living in war zones or in areas where natural disasters are likely to occur, internally displaced ethnic minorities, asylum seekers and refugees are at high risk of developing post-traumatic stress disorder. This study aimed to examine the issue of post-traumatic stress disorder. For this purpose, the literature review method was utilized.

Keywords: Trauma, Stress Disorder, Psychological.

1. Introduction

Human beings are the only creatures who are aware of the inevitability of death (Yalom, 2008 s.17). This insight has the potential to lead to paralyzing terror, as it conflicts with the species' biologically programmed desire for survival (Becker, 1973, s. 172). The "Terror Management Theory" (TMT) was developed to manage this fear, suggesting that people rely on an anxiety buffer consisting of three interrelated psychological constructs (Greenberg et al., 1986, s.201): (1) a cultural worldview that gives meaning, order, and purpose to life, (2) a sense of self-esteem that gives a real or symbolic sense of immortality and (3) relationships associated with protection from harm. This anxiety buffer enables individuals to maintain a state of psychological composure in the face of mortality concerns when it works effectively.

Anxiety Buffer Disruption Theory (ABDT), a derivative of TMT, claims that trauma has the potential to endanger healthy anxiety buffer process because traumatic experiences inherently

involve direct or indirect confrontation with death. (Pyszczynski and Kesebir, 2011, s.18-19). Therefore, ADBT states that when a person's anxiety buffer is debilitated by the experience of trauma, posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD: Posttraumatic Stress Disorder) is caused by experiences of death anxiety (Yalom, 2008 s. 18).

The most prominent theories of PTSD currently informing clinical application emphasize that it results from difficulties in integrating a traumatic experience into pre-traumatic meaning structures (Brewin et al., 2010; Conway, 2005; Dalgleish, 2004; Ehlers & Clark, 2000; Horowitz, 1997). While each theory suggests different psychological mechanisms to explain these difficulties, they all agree that one of the reasons why individuals with PTSD have a difficult time internalizing or assimilating their trauma into pre-traumatic meaning structures is that traumatic experiences often involve a threat towards the person's survival.

The aim of this study is to examine the issue of posttraumatic stress disorder. In accordance with this purpose, literature review method was utilized.

2. History of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder

For nearly 4,000 years, the emotional effects of exposure to extreme stressors have been recorded in historical accounts, clinical records, and western literature (Figley, 1993, s. xx). While the scientific and clinical literature on posttraumatic stress reactions increased rapidly in the nineteenth century, the inclusion of posttraumatic stress disorder in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (APA, 1980) accelerated the empirical and systematic investigation of victims of war, natural and man-made disasters, and civil violence (Eth and Pynoos, 1985, s. 33).

Pierre Janet, recognized as the first psychologist to investigate and treat posttraumatic stress reactions, began to examine the processes by which traumatic experience can lead to psychopathology in the early 1880s and identified many posttraumatic stress symptoms that are

very similar to PTSD today (van der Kolk and van der Hart, 1989, s. 1530). These include dissociative symptoms, memory impairment, "attachment to the trauma" and "numbing and exhaustion" (van der Kolk & van der Hart, 1989: 1533).

The widespread psychopathology observed in war veterans following the Second World War signified a change in psychiatrists' understanding of the causes and treatment of mental illness. It was accepted that environmental stress contributed to psychological maladjustment and that directive intervention could improve outcomes (Grob, 1991, s. 428). During this period, the American Psychiatric Association (APA) Nomenclature and Statistics Committee included severe stress reaction as a psychiatric diagnosis in the first edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-I; APA, 1952) (Saigh and Bremner, 1999, s. 9). The DSM-I stated that severe stress reaction occurs after "severe physical demands or extreme stress, such as war or civil disaster (fire, earthquake, explosion, etc.)" (APA, 1952, s. 40). Besides, the guidelines stated that "in many cases this diagnosis is valid for people who have previously been more or less normal and are experiencing unbearable stress" (APA, 1952, s. 40). Although the cause of severe stress reaction has been identified as an extreme stressor, the DSM-I has not defined operational criteria to formulate a reliable diagnosis of "severe stress reaction" (Saigh and Bremner, 1999, s. 11).

In the second edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-II; APA; 1968), severe stress reaction was replaced by a new classification, transient situational disturbance. According to DSM-II, transient situational disturbance consisted of "transient disorders of any severity (including those of psychotic proportions) occurring in individuals with no underlying mental disorder and representing an acute response to overwhelming environmental stress" (APA, 1968, s. 48). The guidelines also stated that the diagnosis of adjustment reaction in childhood, adolescence or adult life was used if the disorder persisted after a stressor was removed. The validity of the transient situational disturbance classification was investigated in a study of 2078 hospitalized Navy personnel aged 17-48 (Looney and Gunderson, 1978, s. 661). The results indicated that clearer operational criteria for diagnosis were needed to ensure the validity of the classification.

Considering the limited reliability, lack of operational definitions, and inadequate coverage of the diagnostic classifications in DSM-I and DSM-II, the APA assigned a team to formulate the third edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-III, APA, 1980) (Saigh and Bremner, 1999, s. 12). The classifications in DSM-I and DSM-II were largely based on psychodynamic theory and utilized psychoanalytic etiological explanations for psychopathology (Mayes & Horowitz, 2005, s.249). On the other hand, DSM-III adopted the diagnostic model used in the medical field, emphasizing "categories of illness rather than blurred boundaries between normal and abnormal behavior, dichotomies rather than dimensions, and clear symptoms rather than underlying etiological mechanisms" (Mayes and Horowitz, 2005, s. 250). Although empirical data were used in the development of DSM-III, many decisions were based on the opinions of the committee members due to the lack of sufficient research in many areas (Widiger vd., 1991, s. 282).

PTSD was introduced as a diagnostic category in DSM-III. According to DSM-III, PTSD was defined as "the development of characteristic symptoms following a psychologically traumatic event that is usually outside the usual range of human experience" (APA, 1980, s. 236). The DSM-III also stated that "the stressor that elicits this syndrome will cause significant symptoms of distress in most people and is usually outside the range of common experiences such as simple bereavement, chronic illness, job loss, or marital conflict" (APA, 1980, s. 236). Characteristic symptoms were categorized into three groups. Re-experiencing symptoms such as intrusive recollections, recurrent nightmares, flashbacks, and intense distress when reminded of the trauma formed the first group. The second group reflects avoidance symptoms, including efforts to avoid trauma-related thoughts or feelings, avoidance of activities and situations that trigger trauma memories, feelings of withdrawal from others, psychogenic amnesia, decreased interest in activities, restricted affective range, and a sense of a shortened future. Symptoms of increased arousal were collected in a third group, which included sleep difficulties, irritability and outbursts of anger, concentration problems, hypervigilance, exaggerated startle response, and physiological reactions when reminded of the traumatic event (APA, 1980, s. 237).

Although DSM-III was widely adopted by practitioners, it was revised in 1983 (Saigh, 1992, s. 3). The DSM-III-R, published in 1987, attempted to address several problems identified in the DSM-III, including unclear wording, inconsistencies, and errors (Williams, 1986, s. 549). A team was gathered in 1988 to formulate the (APA, 1994) DSM-IV to synchronize revisions of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual with updates to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10; World Health Organization, 1992) ((Saigh & Bremner, 1999, s. 12). The approach in which the DSM-IV was developed differed from previous versions. In this case, the importance of empirical data was emphasized more, while the experiences and clinical judgments of the team members were minimized (Widiger vd., 1991, s. 284).

There is more information in the DSM-IV on associated features and disorders. The DSM-IV explains that PTSD can be associated with feelings of survivor's guilt and that PTSD symptoms can cause difficulties in interpersonal relationships leading to conflict, divorce, or job loss in relation to associated features and mental disorders. In cases where PTSD is caused by an interpersonal stressor, the most common associated symptoms were identified, including impaired affect modulation, somatic complaints, and social withdrawal (APA, 1994, s. 465). Besides, the mental disorders that frequently accompany PTSD were defined as major depressive disorder, substance-related disorders, panic disorder, agoraphobia, obsessive-compulsive disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, social phobia, specific phobia, and bipolar disorder ((APA, 1994: s.465).

Owens and Chard (2003) administered the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale (CAPS-SX; Blake et al., 1995), the Schedule of Nonadaptive and Adaptive Personality (SNAP; Clark, 1996), and the Structured Clinical Interview for the DSM-IV Nonpatient version (First et al., 1996) to 89 female adults who reported being sexually abused as children. In this sample of treatment-seekers, 89% met DSM-IV criteria for current PTSD. The prevalence of current and lifetime depression was 43% and 81%, respectively. Depression and avoidant personality disorder are important predictors of PTSD (Owens & Chard, 2003, s. 1077). Regarding associated features, DSM-IV states that individuals with PTSD may have increased physiological arousal as well as increased somatic complaints and general medical conditions.

Regarding specific cultural and age characteristics of PTSD, the DSM-IV states that rates of PTSD may be increased in recent immigrants from areas of "significant social unrest and civil conflict" (APA, 1994, s. 465). With specific reference to children, the DSM-IV elaborated on the DSM-III-R and added the recommendation that children's symptoms be "carefully evaluated with reports from parents, teachers, and other observers". The DSM-IV also states that "In children, the feeling of a shortened future may be manifested by the belief that life will be too short to include becoming an adult" (APA, 1994, s. 466).

Şahin et al. (2007, s. 335-345), in a study with adolescents aged 12-16 years, examined the determinants and symptoms of PTSD following an earthquake in Türkiye. The results showed that adolescents who were closer to the epicenter of the earthquake scored higher on measures of impact, posttraumatic stress, and negative school performance. More morbidity was observed in girls compared to boys. Finally, negative school performance was the best predictor of posttraumatic stress symptoms in adolescents. This finding is consistent with the DSM-IV recommendation to include teacher reports in the assessment of children's posttraumatic symptoms because "observing students' behavior in these environments can be crucial for selecting those who may need immediate psychological support" (Şahin et al., 2007: s.343).

PTSD prevalence rates are estimated at 8% of the adult population in the United States, according to the DSM-IV. The highest rates of PTSD are seen among victims of rape, military conflict, and captivity, and "ethnically or politically motivated detention and genocide" (APA, 1994: s.466). The DSM-IV states that PTSD can occur at any age and that the onset of symptoms usually occurs within the first 3 months following the trauma, although this can vary widely. The manual states that symptoms of re-experiencing, avoidance and hyperarousal may change over the course of the disorder. The DSM-IV also states that the duration of symptoms varies, with full recovery occurring within three months in about half of cases, while in other symptoms persist for 12 months or more following the trauma (APA, 1994).

Perkonigg et al. (2005, s. 1322) investigated the course of PTSD in a community sample of 125 adolescents and young adults in Germany. Participants were assessed for PTSD

symptomatology and comorbid disorders at baseline and 34-50 months later. Follow-up results showed that 52% of PTSD cases recovered. Participants with a chronic course of PTSD were more likely to have experienced additional traumatic event(s) during the follow-up period and had higher rates of avoidance symptoms at baseline. Finally, chronic PTSD was significantly associated with comorbid somatoform disorder and other anxiety disorders.

The DSM-IV states that the most prominent factors affecting the likelihood of developing PTSD are defined as "the severity, duration and proximity of the individual's exposure to the traumatic event" (APA, 1994, s. 466). Finally, DSM-IV emphasizes that variables such as social support, family history, childhood experiences, personality variables and pre-existing mental disorders may affect the development of PTSD (APA, 1994, s.468). The DSM-IV states that individuals with a family history of PTSD or a history of depression in first-degree relatives have a high risk of developing PTSD (APA, 1994, s.469).

Since the publication of the DSM-IV in 1994, several studies have been carried out with a wide range of traumatized populations. For example, Saigh et al. (2006, s.333) compared the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-III (WISC-III; Wechsler, 1991) scores of traumatized youth with PTSD to those of a comparison group of trauma-exposed youth without PTSD. All groups had no additional major childhood psychiatric disorders. The PTSD group scored significantly lower than the comparison groups on the verbal subtests, but not on the performance subtests. There was no significant difference between the scores of the trauma-exposed PTSD-negatives and the non-trauma-exposed control group. Accordingly, Saigh et al. (2006, s.335) concluded that PTSD, but not a history of trauma exposure in the absence of PTSD, is associated with lower verbal IQ.

Saigh et al. (2007, s.29-37) applied the State-Trait Anger Expression Inventory (STAXI; Spielberger, 1996) to youth with PTSD between the ages of 6-18, traumatized youth without PTSD, and a non-traumatized control group. The results showed that youth with PTSD had significantly higher scores on the STAXI State, Trait, and Anger Expression scales. On the other hand, non-significant differences emerged when comparing the scores of traumatized PTSD negatives and controls.

Similarly, Bremner et al. (1993, s.1016) compared the memory functioning of Vietnam veterans with combat-related PTSD to matched controls without PTSD. The Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-III-R (SCID; Spitzer et al., 1987) was used to determine the presence of PTSD. The results revealed that intelligence scores did not differ significantly between the groups. The PTSD group scored significantly lower on the Wechsler Memory Scale logical memory (verbal) measures for immediate and delayed memory. Besides, the PTSD group showed significantly lower scores on the visual scale for total remind, continuous long-term retrieval, long-term retrieval, and long-term storage, and on the verbal scale for total reminding, long-term storage, long-term retrieval, and delayed reminding on the Selective Remind Test. The findings revealed that PTSD patients have short-term memory problems.

Galea et al. (2002, s.982-987), referring to September 11, 2001, examined the prevalence and correlates of acute PTSD among 978 adults residing in Manhattan during the attack. Participants were contacted 35-94 days after the attacks using random digit dial telephone sampling procedures and administered the PTSD module of the National Women's Study (Kilpatrick et al., 1998, s.807). Results showed that 7.5% of the sample reported symptoms consistent with a diagnosis of PTSD related to the terrorist attacks. Similarly, Schlenger et al. (2002, s.582) used random number search method to identify 2273 adults in New York City or Washington, D.C. 30-60 days after the September 11 attacks. Using the Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Checklist (Weathers et al., 1993, s.83), Schlenger et al. (2002, s.583) reported that the prevalence of probable PTSD in New York City was 11.2%. In the context of the 9/11 terrorist attacks, Hoven et al. (2005, s.545-551) conducted group administrations of the Diagnostic Interview Schedule Predictive Scales for Children (Lucas et al., 2001, s.444) to investigate the prevalence and correlates of PTSD and five other psychological disorders among 8246 randomly selected New York City public school students in grades 4 through 12. Hoven et al. (2005, s.548) reported that 10.6% of the sample met criteria for possible PTSD 6 months after the assault.

3. Diagnosis, Epidemiology, Comorbidity and Socio-Economic Costs of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

3.1. Diagnosis

PTSD is a debilitating psychological condition that can develop in some individuals after trauma. APA (2013: 271) defines a traumatic experience as "an event involving actual or threatened death, serious injury, or exposure to sexual violence, either directly or indirectly". Therefore, some examples of trauma include serious accidents, natural or man-made disasters, life-threatening illnesses, or physical or sexual assaults. For a diagnosis of PTSD, an individual must show signs of aggression, avoidance, negative changes in cognitions and mood, and changes in arousal and reactivity in response to a traumatic experience (APA, 2013, s.272).

Intrusion symptoms may take the form of recurrent and involuntary memories, distressing nightmares, flashbacks, or marked physiological reactions to internal or external reminders of the trauma, while avoidance symptoms characterize the disorder, as do negative changes in cognition and mood from such reminders (e.g., trauma-related thoughts, feelings, mental images, objects, places, people, etc.). These include an inability to remind important aspects of the traumatic experience, negative beliefs and expectations about oneself or the world, reduced interest in activities, feelings of alienation or feelings of fear, terror, anger, guilt, or shame.

A final feature of PTSD is the changes in arousal and reactivity that can result in irritable or aggressive behavior, self-harm, hyper-vigilance, concentration problems or sleep disturbance. More importantly, these symptoms must persist for more than 1 month after the trauma and cause clinical distress or functional impairment to be diagnosed as PTSD. If symptoms last longer than 3 months, they are considered to represent a chronic disorder. In cases where symptoms do not appear until 6 months after a traumatic experience, the resulting condition is referred to as delayed-onset PTSD (APA, 2013, s.274).

3.2. Epidemiology

Prevalence studies in North and South America, Europe, Africa, Asia, Africa, Asia, and Australia estimate that 60-90% of the general population has experienced at least one trauma in their lifetime (Atwoli et al., 2013; Kawakami et al., 2014; Kilpatrick et al., 2013; Mills et al., 2011, Zlotnick et al., 2006). While most individuals show some symptoms of PTSD after a traumatic experience, the vast majority recover spontaneously within 3 to 6 months after the experience (Foa & Riggs, 1995; s. 63; Yehuda & LeDoux, 2007, s.22-23). In conclusion, 12-month prevalence rates for PTSD remain relatively low, ranging from 0.4-3.8% worldwide (Karam et al., 2014). While this global variation in prevalence rates may be associated with ethnic differences in the level of trauma exposure (Roberts et al., 2011, s.74), geographical and political factors may also influence PTSD prevalence. For example, individuals living in war zones (Pham et al., 2004, s.604 or areas where natural disasters are more likely to occur (Galea et al., 2005, s.83), internally displaced ethnic minorities (Thapa and Hauff, 2005, s.673 asylum seekers (Hinton et al., 2006, s.406) and refugees (Gerritsen et al., 2006, s.22) are at higher risk of developing this condition.

Several pre-traumatic, traumatic, and post-traumatic factors need to be taken into consideration when predicting the onset of PTSD (Brewin et al., 2000, s.748; DiGangi et al., 2013, s.67). For example, a significant body of research suggests that lower cognitive ability (Betts et al., 2012, s.933), prior trauma exposure (van Zuiden et al., 2012, s.310), or a history of personal or family psychopathology (Sandweiss et al., 2011, s.496) predict more severe posttraumatic stress responses to trauma. Peritraumatic factors such as the degree of life threat or physical injury experienced during the trauma also increase the likelihood of developing PTSD (Schnurr et al., 2004, s.94).

Consequently, traumatic experiences involving grief, assault or violence seem particularly likely to lead to the emergence of PTSD (Breslau et al., 1998, s.631). Experiences of dissociation (Murray et al., 2002, s.367), mental derangement (Dunmore et al., 1999, s.809) or mental defeat (Ehlers et al., 2000, s.320) during trauma are also associated with worse prognosis. Similarly, perceived lack of social support (Ulmann and Filipas, 2001, s.370), unrealistic negative evaluations of self, others, or the world (Dunmore et al., 2001, s. 1063), or

excessive feelings of anger, guilt, or shame (Andrews et al., 2000, s.70) reduce the likelihood of spontaneous recovery.

3.3. Comorbidity

In cases where PTSD develops, the readjustment process is likely to be further complicated by the presence of at least one comorbid psychiatric disorder (APA, 2013; Kessler et al., 2005, s.622). Comorbidity between PTSD and depression is particularly high (Stander et al., 2014, s.89), with a significant proportion of individuals with PTSD also suffering from panic disorder (Barrera et al., 2013, s.170), social phobia (Zayfert et al., 2005, s.99) or substance use disorder (Jacobsen et al., 2001, s.1185). A minority of individuals may also experience more serious mental health problems such as schizophrenia or bipolar disorder (Grubaugh et al., 2011, s.888).

While the causal relationship between PTSD and some of these comorbid psychiatric disorders is most likely bidirectional, epidemiologic research shows that at least in cases of comorbid depression, PTSD precedes and thus triggers depression (Kessler et al., 1995, s.1050). However, findings on this topic are complex (Aderka et al., 2013, s.378), thus suggest that the reciprocal relationship between depressive symptoms and PTSD most likely explains the high comorbidity (Erickson et al., 2001, s.48).

Individuals with PTSD are also at risk of suffering from a variety of physical health problems, including cardio-respiratory problems, gastro-intestinal complications (Mayer, 2007, s.1963) and chronic pain. While the etiology of these medical conditions is complex, it is likely that dysregulated immune system functioning resulting from the chronic mental and physiological stress associated with PTSD contributes to their occurrence (Altemus et al., 2006, s.180). Because of such concurrent health challenges, individuals with PTSD experience more quality-of-life impairments than those with anxiety disorders (Olatunji et al., 2007, s.575). In fact, WHO (2004) estimates that this costs approximately 3.5 million years of 'healthy life' each year.

3.4. Socio Economic Costs

Considering the wide range of mental and physical health problems associated with PTSD, it is not surprising that PTSD is one of the costliest mental health disorders. The estimated annual

loss of productivity in the United States has been found to exceed US\$3 billion (Brunello et al., 2001, s.155). While the current financial burden of PTSD in the UK is unknown, in 1995 the Department of Health estimated that stress-related conditions such as PTSD resulted in 91 million working days lost each year, costing industry £3.7 billion. Similarly, Holmes (1994, s.1070) estimated that 'neurotic disorders' such as PTSD cost the National Health Service £5.6 billion a year. Based on these figures, the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE, 2005: 43) concluded that "PTSD represents an enormous economic burden for families, the NHS and society as a whole".

4. Psychological Processes Playing a Role in Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

Considering the significant socio-economic costs associated with PTSD, there is a need for cost-effective treatments for the condition (NICE, 2005, s.44). Researchers have already formulated several theoretical models to inform psychological interventions for the disorder (Brewin & Holmes, 2003, s.340; Dalgleish, 2004, s.235). According to Dalgleish (2004, s.228-245), one of the criteria for evaluating these theories is the extent to which they can explain the underlying clinical and research data of PTSD. Therefore, a complete model of PTSD should be able to precisely explain the mechanisms through which natural or goal-directed recovery from symptoms occurs in addition to explaining individual differences in pre, during and posttraumatic factors that lead to the development and maintenance of chronic or delayed-onset versions of the condition.

For this purpose, researchers and clinicians have identified PTSD with disorders in a range of psychological processes (Brewin & Holmes, 2003, s.344). For example, individuals with PTSD have been shown to exhibit an attentional bias in relation to threat (Iacoviello et al., 2014, s.236). While such attentional biases can lead to exaggerated fear responses (Fani et al., 2012, s.538), PTSD has often been associated with other strong emotional responses such as anger, guilt, or shame (Andrews et al., 2000, s.71). In some cases, these emotions may overlap with the actual emotions experienced during the most intense moments of the trauma, but in other cases, feelings of anger, guilt, or shame may result from excessive negative cognitions about oneself, others, or the world after the trauma (Kleim et al., 2007, s.1459).

Individuals with PTSD who are overcome by such intense emotions may adopt various maladaptive coping strategies to cope with their distress (Ehlers & Clark, 2000, s.321). The vast majority of these involve efforts to suppress unwanted thoughts, feelings, or memories. In their most extreme forms, attempts to avoid trauma memories can result in dissociative symptoms including emotional numbing, derealization, depersonalization, or 'out-of-body' experiences. Despite these potentially extreme responses to trauma, individuals with PTSD may begin to create their life narratives around their traumatic experiences, thus making it one of the most central aspects of their identity (Brewin, 2011, s.224; Sutherland & Bryant, 2005, s.593). Perceived or actual problems in one's social support network may also accompany such changes in sense of self (Ulmann & Filipas, 2001, s.371).

Accordingly, a variety of psychological mechanisms are involved in the development and maintenance of PTSD, including attention, affect, cognition, coping strategies, dissociation, identity formation, and social support (Brewin & Holmes, 2003, s.345). While many of these processes are involved in the etiology of a range of other psychiatric disorders, a paradoxical impairment in autobiographical memory is thought to distinguish PTSD from other mental health conditions (Brewin, 2011, s.229). The paradox is that although the traumatic event is strongly linked to the individual's personal identity (Sutherland & Bryant, 2005, s.594), the trauma memory itself is found to be inconsistent with the perception that it represents an important turning point in their lives and is not sufficiently integrated into their autobiographical memory (Jones et al., 2007, s.158). This situation is valid even though the trauma memory is highly emotional and rich in sensory details (Whalley et al., 2007, s.333). As a result of the lack of integration in autobiographical memory, conscious reminding of the trauma memory becomes scattered and fragmented, while involuntary retrieval is strengthened (Buck et al., 2007, s.268). Due to the lack of integration into autobiographical memory, when the trauma memory is involuntarily triggered, it is experienced as if it is happening right now. This leads to intrusive memories and flashbacks, which are symptomatic in PTSD (APA, 2013).

Even though the above-mentioned disorder in autobiographical memory is specific to PTSD, this does not mean that trauma memories have a special status because they are related to traumatic events or that the processes involved in these memories are different from the

mechanisms hypothesized in normal memory (Brewin, 2011, s.230). In fact, non-traumatic memories themselves can be highly emotionally charged and rich in sensory detail, but their content can be disorganized and fragmented (Fernyhough, 2012, s.133). The distinctive feature of trauma memories is that they should involve the feeling of reliving the actual traumatic event. Therefore, a complete theory of PTSD should be able to account for this unique feature of trauma memories and explain them in terms of the mechanisms underlying normal memory (Brewin, 2011, s.232).

Another feature of trauma memories that any comprehensive model of PTSD should be able to explain is that they can change over time (Brewin, 2011, s.232). For example, a study revealed that in delayed-onset PTSD cases, memories of events that were not initially perceived as traumatic may acquire traumatic features through various processes, including reappraisal and sensitization (Andrews et al., 2009, s.770). Based on such findings, it seems likely that different mechanisms play a role in the etiology of sudden and delayed onset PTSD. Therefore, it is important that any theory of PTSD can account for these different pathways to the disorder (Brewin, 2011, s.233).

5. Psychological Treatments Related to Posttraumatic Stress Disorder

Brewin (2003, s.154), who evaluated the processes involved in the development and maintenance of PTSD, concluded that it is a hybrid disorder consisting of multiple psychological mechanisms. Therefore, recovery from PTSD depends on targeting multiple processes (Brewin & Holmes, 2003, s.367). While various psychopharmacological medications have been shown to be effective in helping individuals manage the symptoms of PTSD (Albucher and Liberzon, 2002, s.368), several randomized controlled trials suggest that trauma-focused psychological interventions are more effective in treating the condition than general, non-trauma-focused therapies (Ehlers et al., 2003, s.1030; Foa et al., 1999). In this context, national guidelines recommend trauma-focused psychological interventions as first-line treatment for PTSD (APA, 2013; NICE, 2005).

In general, trauma-focused psychological interventions consist of prolonged exposure therapy (Foa & Rothbaum, 1998, s.109), cognitive therapy (Ehlers & Clark, 2000, s.322), or some

combination thereof. In prolonged exposure therapy, patients are supported, within the safety of the therapeutic environment, to confront objects and places related to their trauma and to recount these memories repeatedly until they become desensitized to the trauma and related stimuli through a process of habituation. A particularly important aspect of therapy is for patients to develop a coherent narrative around the most emotionally charged, vivid, scattered, and fragmented moments of their trauma memory because processing these aspects of their trauma memory allows them to integrate into their autobiographical memory. Thanks to this integration process, conscious reminding of the trauma memory increases and involuntary reminding decreases, thereby regaining a sense of competence and trust in the world (Foa & Rothbaum, 1998, s.111).

While long-term exposure therapy can indirectly lead to a reduction in trauma-related negative cognitions about oneself, others and the world, cognitive therapy is directly concerned with targeting these negative evaluations. Especially, cognitive restructuring techniques aim to force the patient to reconsider their overly negative interpretations of the trauma and its effects, to gain a more balanced and realistic perspective. This can be particularly important in cases where appraisal-based anger, guilt or shame prevents the patient from participating effectively in exposure work (Ehlers & Clark, 2000, s.323).

Dalgleish (2004: 231) concluded that, considering the conclusive evidence supporting long-term exposure therapy, cognitive therapy, and their variations, "there is little evidence to support the clear clinical superiority of any one form of active treatment over another, or the superiority of combined treatments over single treatments". While the results of trauma-focused psychological interventions for PTSD are impressive, treatment is usually successful in only 70% of cases (Dalgleish, 2004, s.231). In some cases, prolonged exposure may even lead to strong feelings of anger, guilt or shame that are counterproductive to recovery (Pitman, et al., 1991, s.19). Considering the possible ineffectiveness or even harmfulness of trauma-focused psychological interventions in 30% of cases, a comprehensive theory of PTSD should be able to explain those who do not respond to this treatment and suggest alternative methods for their treatment (Jaycox & Foa, 1996, s.179-180).

7. Conclusion

Individuals have been exposed to traumatic experiences in time, ranging from natural disasters to man-made, intentional acts of violence. The psychological effects of extreme stress have been documented, including nightmares, increased startle response, avoidance behavior and cognitive/developmental disorders. The classification of stress response syndrome has been pursued by mental health and medical professionals for a long time. While DSM-III included PTSD as a diagnostic classification in 1980, there was no reference to children or adolescents in the description of the disorder.

In later revisions to the DSM, information on the expression of PTSD among young people was included. However, the DSM-IV PTSD field survey did not include youth under 15 years of age. While there have been several studies examining the functioning of traumatized youth since the publication of the DSM-IV, additional data-driven research on the expression of PTSD in youth is needed.

In a meta-analysis of the PTSD literature, three categories of risk factors were identified that were regularly associated with trauma exposure and the development of PTSD compared to adults: Pre-existing psychiatric disorders, family history of psychopathology and childhood trauma. Cross-referencing the literature reviewed in this context, a range of traumatic events, including criminal victimization, war, and accidents/disasters, represent various risk factors for PTSD. The sequelae of a traumatic event can change depending on the type and severity of the stressor. The degree of exposure to the same event, whether organic or man-made, may also explain differences in psychological effects.

The reviewed literature also shows that some demographic variables such as gender, age and socioeconomic status are risk factors for PTSD. Among victims of crime, war and accidents/disasters, exposure to multiple traumas significantly increased the risk of PTSD. Lastly, regarding comorbidity, more focused and controlled research is needed to better understand the etiology, course, and treatment of PTSD.

8. References

- Aderka IM., Gillihan SJ, McLean CP, Foa EB. The relationship between posttraumatic and depressive symptoms during prolonged exposure with and without cognitive restructuring for the treatment of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*. 2013; 81, 375-382.
- Albucher RC, Liberzon I. Psychopharmacological treatment in PTSD: A critical review. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*. 2002; 36, 355-367.
- Altemus M, Dhabhar FS, Yang R. Immune function in PTSD. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 2006; 1071, 167-183.
- American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. Washington, DC: Author; 1952.
- American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (2nd ed.). Washington, DC: Author; 1968.
- American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (3rd ed.). Washington, DC: Author; 1980.
- American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (4th ed.). Washington, DC: Author; 1994.
- American Psychiatric Association. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (5th ed.). ("An Overview of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM) - Verywell Mind") Washington, DC: Author; 2013.
- Andrews B, Brewin CR, Rose S, Kirk M. Predicting PTSD symptoms in victims of violent crime: The role of shame, anger, and childhood abuse. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. 2000; 109, 69-73.
- Andrews B, Brewin CR, Stewart L, Philpott R, Hejdenberg J. Comparison of immediate and delayed-onset posttraumatic stress disorder in military veterans. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. 2009; 118, 767-777.
- Atwoli L, Stein DJ, Williams DR, McLaughlin KA, Petukhova M, Kessler RC, Koenen KC. Trauma, and posttraumatic stress disorder in South Africa: Analysis from the South African Stress and Health

- Study. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2013; 13, 182-193.
- Barrera TL, Graham DP, Dunn NJ, Teng EJ. Influence of trauma history on panic and posttraumatic stress disorder in returning veterans. *Psychological Services*. 2013; 10, 168-176.
- Becker E. *The denial of death*. New York: The Free Press; 1973.
- Betts KS, Williams GM, Najman JM, Bor W, Alati R. Pretrauma verbal ability at five years of age and the risk of post-traumatic stress disorder in adult males and females. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*. 2012; 46, 933-939.
- "Blake DD, Weathers FW, Nagy LM, Kaloupek DG, Gusman FD, Charney DS, Keane TM." ("EMDR vs Supportive Therapy in Relapse Prevention in Traumatized Bipolar ...") The development of a clinician-administered PTSD scale. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 1995; 8, 75-90.
- Bremner JD, Scott TM, Delaney RC, Southwick SM, Mason JW, Johnson DR., . . . Charney DS. Deficits in short-term memory in posttraumatic stress disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1993; 150, 1015-1019
- Breslau N, Kessler R, Chilcoat HD, Schultz LR, Davis GC, Andreski P. Trauma, and posttraumatic stress disorder in the community: The 1996 Detroit Area Survey of Trauma. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 1998; 55, 626-632.
- Brewin CR, Andrews B, Valentine JD. Meta-analysis of risk factors for posttraumatic stress disorder in trauma-exposed adults. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*. 2000; 68, 748-766.
- "Brewin CR, Gregory JD, Lipton M, Burgess N. Intrusive images in psychological disorders: characteristics, neural mechanisms, and treatment implications." ("Prefrontal-posterior coupling while observing the suffering of other ...") *Psychological Review*. 2010; 117, 210-232.
- Brewin CR, Holmes EA. Psychological theories of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2003; 23, 339-376.
- Brewin CR. *Posttraumatic stress disorder: Malady or myth?* New Haven, CT: Yale University Press; 2003.
- Brewin CR. *The nature and significance of memory disturbance in*

- posttraumatic stress disorder. Annual Review of Clinical Psychology. 2011; 7, 203-227.
- Brunello N, Davidson JR, Deahl M, Kessler RC, Mendlewicz J, Racagni G., ... Zohar J. Posttraumatic stress disorder: Diagnosis, epidemiology, comorbidity, social consequences, biology, and treatment. Neuropsychobiology. 2001; 43, 150-162
- Buck N, Kindt M, van den Hout M, Steens L, Linders C. Perceptual memory representations and memory fragmentation as predictors of posttrauma symptoms. Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy. 2007; 35, 259-272.
- Clark LA. Schedule for Nonadaptive and Adaptive Personality: Manual for administration, scoring, and interpretation. ("Clark, L. A. (1993). Schedule for Nonadaptive and Adaptive Personality ...") Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press; 1996.
- Conway MA. Memory and the self. Journal of Memory and Language. 2005; 53, 594-628.
- Dalgleish T. Cognitive approaches to posttraumatic stress disorder: the evolution of multirepresentational theorizing. Psychological Bulletin. 2004; 130, 228-260.
- DiGangi J, Guffanti G, McLaughlin KA, Koenen KC. Considering trauma exposure in the context of genetics studies of posttraumatic stress disorder: A systematic review. Biology of Mood and Anxiety Disorders. 2013; 3. No Pagination.
- Dunmore E, Clark DM, Ehlers A. A prospective investigation of the role of cognitive factors in persistent posttraumatic stress disorder after physical or sexual assault. Behaviour Research and Therapy. 2001; 39, 1063-1084.
- Dunmore E, Clark DM, Ehlers A. Cognitive factors involved in the onset and maintenance of PTSD. Behaviour Research and Therapy. 1999; 37, 809-829.
- Ehlers A, Clark DM, Hackmann A, McManus F, Fennell M, Herbert C, Mayou R. A randomized controlled trial of cognitive therapy, self-help booklet, and repeated assessment as early interventions for PTSD. Archives of General Psychiatry. 2003; 60, 1024-1032.

- Ehlers A, Clark DM. A cognitive model of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*. 2000; 38, 319-345.
- Ehlers A, Maercker A, Boos A. Posttraumatic stress disorder following political imprisonment: the role of mental defeat, alienation, and perceived permanent change. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. 2000; 109, 45-55.
- "Erickson DJ, Wolfe J, King DW, King LA, Sharkansky EJ." ("Patients with Combat-related and War-related Posttraumatic Stress ...") Posttraumatic stress disorder and depression symptomatology in a sample of Gulf War veterans: A prospective analysis. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*. 2001; 69, 41-49.
- Eth S, Pynoos RS. (Eds.). Post-traumatic stress disorder in children. United States of America: American Psychiatric Association; 1985.
- Fani N, Tone EB, Phifer J, Norrholm SD, Bradley B, Ressler KJ, ... Jovanovic T. Attention bias toward threat is associated with exaggerated fear expression and impaired extinction in PTSD. *Psychological Medicine*. 2012; 42, 533-543.
- Fernyhough C. *Pieces of light: The new science of memory*. London: Profile Books; 2012.
- Figley CR. Foreword. In J.P. Wilson & B. Raphael (Eds.), *International handbook of traumatic stress syndromes* (pp. xvii-xx). New York: Plenum Press; 1993.
- First MB, Spitzer RL, Gibbon M, Williams JBW. *Structured clinical interview for DSM-IV axis I disorders—nonpatient edition*. New York: Biometrics Research Department, New York State Psychiatric Institute; 1996.
- Foa EB, Ehlers A, Clark DM, Tolin DF, Orsillo SM. The Posttraumatic Cognitions Inventory: Development and validation. *Psychological Assessment*. 1999; 11, 303.
- Foa EB, Riggs DS. Posttraumatic stress disorder following assault: Theoretical considerations and empirical findings. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*. 1995; 4, 61-65.
- Foa EB, Rothbaum BA. *Treating the trauma of rape: Cognitive behavioral*

- therapy for PTSD. New York: Guilford Press; 1998.
- Galea S, Ahren J, Resnick H, Kilpatrick D, Bucuvalias M, Gold J, Vlahov D. Psychological sequelae of the September 11 terrorist attack in New York City. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2002; 346, 982-987.
- Galea S, Nandi A, Vlahov D. The epidemiology of posttraumatic stress disorder after disasters. *Epidemiological Review*. 2005; 27, 78-91.
- Gerritsen AA, Bramsen I, Deville W, van Willigen LH, Hovens JE, van derPloeg HM. Physical and mental health of Afghan, Iranian and Somali asylum seekers and refugees living in the Netherlands. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*. 2006; 41, 18-26.
- Greenberg J, Pyszczynski T, Solomon S. The causes and consequences of a need for self-esteem: A terror management theory. In *Public self and private self* (pp.189-212). Springer New York; 1986.
- "Grob GN. Origins of DSM-I: A Study in Appearance and Reality." ("IL DSM-5: l'edizione italiana | Rivista di Psichiatria") *The American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1991; 148, 421-431.
- "Grubaugh AL, Zinzow HM, Paul L, Egede LE, Frueh BC." ("Protective Factors Associated With Post-traumatic Outcomes in ...") *Trauma exposure and posttraumatic stress disorder in adults with severe mental illness: A critical review*. *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2011; 31, 883-899
- Hinton DE, Chhean D, Pich V, Pollack MH, Orr SP, Pitman RK. Assessment of posttraumatic stress disorder in Cambodian refugees using the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale: Psychometric properties and symptom severity. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2006; 19, 405-411.
- Holmes J. Psychotherapy - a luxury the NHS cannot afford? More expensive not to treat. *British Medical Journal*. 1994; 309, 1070-1071.
- Horowitz MJ. *Stress response syndromes: PTSD, grief, and adjustment disorders*. New York: Jason Aronson; 1997.
- Hoven CW, Duarte CS, Lucas CP, Wu P, Mandell DJ, Goodwin RD, ...Susser

- E. Psychopathology among New York City public school children 6 months after September 11. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2005; 62, 545-551. doi: 10.1001/archpsyc.62.5.545
- Iacoviello BM, Wu G, Abend R, Murrough JW, Feder A, Fruchter E, ... Charney DS. ("Prevention of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Following Trauma by ...") Attention Bias Variability and Symptoms of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2014; 27, 232-239
- Jacobsen LK, Southwick SM, Kosten TR. Substance use disorders in patients with posttraumatic stress disorder: a review of the literature. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2001; 158, 1184-1190.
- Jaycox LH, Foa EB. Obstacles in implementing exposure therapy for PTSD: Case discussions and practical solutions. *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*. 1996; 3, 176-184
- Jones C, Harvey AG, Brewin CR. The organisation and content of trauma memories in survivors of road traffic accidents. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*. 2007; 45, 151-162.
- Karam EG, Friedman MJ, Hil ED, Kessler RC, McLaughlin KA, Petukhova M, ... Koenen KC. Cumulative traumas and risk thresholds: 12-month PTSD in the World Mental Health (WMH) surveys. *Depression and Anxiety*. 2014; 31,130–142.
- "Kawakami N, Tsuchiya M, Umeda M, Koenen KC, Kessler RC." ("An Open Pilot Trial of Written Exposure Therapy for Patients With Post ...") Trauma and posttraumatic stress disorder in Japan: Results from the World Mental Health Japan Survey. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*. 2014; 53, 157-165.
- Kessler RC, Chiu WC, Demier O, Walters EE. Prevalence, severity, and comorbidity of 12-month DSM-IV disorders in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2005; 62, 617-627.
- "Kessler RC, Sonnega A, Bromet E, Hughes M, Nelson CB." ("Urbanization and mental health - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)") Posttraumatic stress disorder in the National Comorbidity Survey.

- Archives of General Psychiatry. 1995; 52, 1048-60.
- Kilpatrick D, Resnick HS, Milanak ME, Miller MW, Keys KM, Friedman MJ. National estimates of exposure to potentially traumatic events and PTSD prevalence using DSM-IV and DSM-5 criteria. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2013; 26, 537-547.
- Kilpatrick DG, Resnick H, Freedy J, Pelcovitz D, Resick P, Roth S, van der Kolk B. Posttraumatic stress disorder field trial: evaluation of the PTSD construct – criteria A through E. In T. Widiger, A. Frances, H. Pincus, R. Ross, M. First, W. Davis, & M. Kline (Eds.). *DSM-IV Sourcebook*, vol. 4. (pp. 803-844). Washington D.C.: American Psychiatric Association; 1998.
- Kleim B, Ehlers A, Glucksman E. Early predictors of chronic post-traumatic stress disorder in assault survivors. *Psychological Medicine*. 2007; 37, 1457-1467.
- Looney JG, Gunderson EK. Transient situational disturbances: course and outcome. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1978; 135, 660-663.
- Lucas CP, Zhang H, Fisher PW, Shaffer D, Regier DA, Narrow WE, . . . Friman P. The DISC Predictive Scales (DPS). *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. (“Home Page: Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry”) 2001; 40, 443-449.
- Mayer EA. Irritable bowel syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2007; 358,1692-1699
- Mayes R, Horowitz AV. DSM-III and the revolution in the classification of mental illness. *Journal of the History of the Behavioral Sciences*. 2005; 41, 249-267. doi: 10.1002 /jhbs.20103
- Mills KL, Mcfarlane AC, Slade T, Creamer M, Silove D, Teesson M, Bryant R. Assessing the prevalence of trauma exposure in epidemiological surveys. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*. 2011; 45, 407-15
- Murray J, Ehlers A, Mayou RA. Dissociation, and post-traumatic stress disorder: Two prospective studies of road traffic accident survivors. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*. 2002; 180, 363-368.

- National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence. Post-traumatic stress disorder: The management of PTSD in adults and children in secondary care. London: National Institute for Clinical Excellence; 2005.
- Olatunji BO, Cisler JM, Tolin DF. Quality of life in the anxiety disorders: A meta-analytic review. ("Quality of life in the anxiety disorders: A meta-analytic review") *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2007; 27, 572-581.
- Owens GP, Chard KM. Comorbidity, and psychiatric diagnoses among women reporting child sexual abuse. *Child Abuse & Neglect*. 2003; 27, 1075-1082. doi:10.1016/S0145-2134(03)00168-6.
- Perkonig A, Pfister H, Stein MB, Hofler M, Lieb R, Maercker A, Wittchen H. Longitudinal course of posttraumatic stress disorder and posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms in a community sample of adolescents and young adults. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 2005; 162, 1320-1327.
- Pham PN, Weinstein HM, Longman T. Trauma and PTSD symptoms in Rwanda: implications for attitudes toward justice and reconciliation. *The Journal of the American Medical Association*. 2004; 292, 602-612.
- Pitman RK, Altman B, Greenwald E, Longpre RE, Macklin ML, Poire RE, Steketee GS. Psychiatric complications during flooding therapy for posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*. 1991; 52, 17-20.
- Pyszczyński T, Kesebir P. Anxiety buffer disruption theory: A terror management account of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*. 2011; 24, 3-26.
- Roberts AL, Gilman SE, Breslau J, Breslau N, Koenen KC. Race/ethnic differences in exposure to traumatic events, development of post-traumatic stress disorder, and treatment-seeking for post-traumatic stress disorder in the United States. *Psychological Medicine*. 2011; 41, 71-83.
- Şahin NH, Batigun AD, Yılmaz B. Psychological symptoms of Turkish children and adolescents after the 1999 earthquake: Exposure, gender,

- location, and time duration. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2007; 20, 335-345.
- Saigh PA, Bremner JD. The history of posttraumatic stress disorder. In P. A. Saigh & J. D. Bremner (Eds.), *Posttraumatic stress disorder: A comprehensive text* (pp. 1-17). Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon; 1999.
- Saigh PA, Yasik AE, Oberfield RO, Halamandaris P, Bremner JD. The intellectual performance of traumatized children and adolescents with or without posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. 2006; 115, 332-340.
- "Saigh PA, Yasik AE, Oberfield RO, Halamandaris P. Self-reported anger among traumatized children and adolescents." ("The Parent Ratings of Traumatized Children With or Without PTSD") *Journal of Psychopathology and Behavioral Assessment*. 2007; 29, 29-37.
- Saigh PA. History, current nosology, and epidemiology. In P.A. Saigh (Ed.), *Posttraumatic stress disorder: A behavioral approach to assessment and treatment* (pp. 1-27). Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon; 1992.
- Sandweiss DA, Slymen DJ, LeardMann CA, Smith B, White MR, Boyko EJ, ... Smith TC. Preinjury psychiatric status, injury severity, and postdeployment posttraumatic stress disorder. *Archives of General Psychiatry*. 2011; 68, 496-504
- Sawchuk CN, Roy-Byrne P, Goldberg J, Manson S, Noonan C, Beals J, Buchwald D. The relationship between post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, and cardiovascular disease in an American Indian tribe. *Psychological Medicine*. 2005; 35, 1785-1794.
- Schlenger WE, Caddell J, Ebert L, Jordan B, Rourke K, Wilson D, . . . Kulka RA. Psychological reactions to terrorist attacks: Findings from the national study of Americans' reactions to September 11. *Journal of the American Medical Association*. 2002; 288, 581-588.
- Schnurr PP, Lunney CA, Sengupta A. Risk factors for the development versus maintenance of posttraumatic stress disorder. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2004; 17, 85-95.

- Spielberger CD. State-trait anger expression inventory manual. Odessa, FL: Psychological Assessment Resources; 1996.
- Spitzer RL, Williams JBW, Gibbon M. Structured Clinical Interview for DSMIII-R. New York, New York State Psychiatric Institute, Biometrics Research; 1987. (“Obesity and depression in adolescence and beyond: reciprocal risks - Nature”)
- Stander VA, Thomsen CJ, Highfill-McRoy RM. Etiology of depression comorbidity in combat-related PTSD: A review of the literature. *Clinical Psychology Review*. 2014; 34, 87-98.
- Sutherland K, Bryant RA. Self- defining memories in posttraumatic stress disorder. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2005; 44, 591-598.
- Thapa SB, Hauff E. Psychological distress among displaced persons during an armed conflict in Nepal. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*. 2005; 40, 672-679.
- Ulmann SE, Filipas HH. Predictors of PTSD symptom severity and social reactions in sexual assault victims. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 2001; 14, 369-389.
- van der Kolk BA, van der Hart O. Pierre Janet and the breakdown of adaptation in psychological trauma. (“Bessel Van Der Kolk CV - Trauma Research Foundation”) *American Journal of Psychiatry*. 1989; 146, 1530-1540.
- van Zuiden M, Geuze E, Willemsen HL, Vermetten E, Maas M, Amarouchi K, ... Heijnen CJ. (“Index Article - BC OSI”) Glucocorticoid receptor pathway components predict posttraumatic stress disorder symptom development: a prospective study. *Biological Psychiatry*. 2012; 71, 309-316.
- Weathers FW, Litz BT, Herman DS, Huska JA, Keane TM. The PTSD Checklist (PCL): reliability, validity, and diagnostic utility. Paper presented at the Annual Conference of the International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies, San Antonio, Texas; 1993.
- Wechsler D. Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – 3rd edition: Manual. San Antonio, TX: The Psychological Corporation; 1991.

- Whalley MG, Farmer E, Brewin CR. Pain flashbacks following the July 7th, 2005, London bombings. *Pain*. 2007; 132, 332-336.
- "Widiger TA, Frances AJ, Pincus HA, Davis WW, First MB." ("Author Response to Re: Complex regional pain syndrome | The BMJ") Toward an empirical classification for the DSM-IV. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. 1991; 100, 280-288.
- Williams JB. DSM-III-R: What's all the fuss about? *Hospital & Community Psychiatry*. 1986; 37, 549-550
- World Health Organization. International statistical classification of disease and related health problems (10th ed.). Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc; 1992.
- World Health Organization. International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems (Vol. 1). World Health Organization; 2004.
- Yalom I. Staring at the sun: Overcoming the dread of death. ("Staring at the Sun: Overcoming the Dread of Death.") London: Piatkus; 2008.
- Yehuda R, LeDoux J. Response variation following trauma: a translational neuroscience approach to understanding PTSD. *Neuron*. 2007; 56, 19-32.
- Zayfert C, DeViva JC, Hofmann SG. Comorbid PTSD and social phobia in a treatment-seeking population: An exploratory study. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*. 2005; 193, 93-101.
- Zlotnick C, Johnson J, Kohn R, Vicente B, Rioseco P, Saldivia S. Epidemiology of trauma, posttraumatic stress disorder and comorbid disorders in Chile. *Psychological Medicine*. 2006; 36, 1523-1533.